

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND WORK MOTIVATION AMONG PUBLIC SERVANTS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF LAZI, SIKUIJOR

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ABSTRACT

This study emphasizes the work-life balance and motivation levels of public employees in the Municipality of Lazi. It focuses on three main areas: the degree of WLB, the degree of motivation, and the connection between these variables and the public employee profile. In addition to national government organizations like the Philippine National Police (PNP) and the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP), the respondents included eighty permanent public personnel from various departments and offices of the Local Government Units (LGUs) in Lazi. The study took a correlational approach in establishing relationships between the public servants' work-life balance and motivation and their profile, using a descriptive-correlational approach to identify the extent of work-life balance and motivation among them. Results show that public employees generally have a moderate work-life balance, with a particularly noticeable increase in work-personal life enhancement.

Keywords: *extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, motivation, WLB*

INTRODUCTION

Achieving a healthy work-life balance has become more difficult for employees across a variety of businesses in today's fast-paced and competitive environment. WLB, crucial for personal and professional satisfaction, is achieved when personal and job demands are managed effectively (Lumunon et al., 2019; Juliarti & Anindita, 2022). Studies suggest that implementing WLB programs can improve employee engagement and performance (Larastrini & Adnyani, 2019). Motivation, essential for task competition, can be intrinsic or extrinsic (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Intrinsic motivation arises from personal

satisfaction in the work itself, while extrinsic motivation comes from external rewards (Deci & Ryan, 2000). WLB positively influences motivation, emphasizing the need to balance both factors for enhanced job performance and employee well-being (Hite & McDonald, 2020).

Prior research has explored work-life balance in various sectors and countries but has often neglected its specific impact on employee motivation in the public sector, especially in the Philippines. Understanding this relationship is crucial for public officials in Lazi, Siquijor, as Filipinos prioritize work-life balance more than their Southeast Asian counterparts. Policymakers can benefit from insights into the factors affecting work-life balance and motivation among public employees, leading to improved service delivery and performance in a supportive work environment.

The purpose of this study is to close the research gap by examining the unique dynamics of motivation and work-life balance among public employees in the Municipality of Lazi, Siquijor. While studies in various sectors and countries have been conducted, there is a lack of research focusing on this topic within the Philippine context, particularly in the public sector. Gaining an understanding of these dynamics is essential to creating solutions that effectively improve work-life balance and employee motivation in this particular setting.

This study aims to consider the relationship between work-life balance and the motivation of public employees in Lazi, Siquijor, who are under pressure to provide essential services. The study intends to investigate this link in order to offer insights that can guide policies and initiatives aimed at enhancing motivation and work-life balance for municipal public employees.

Research Questions

The study is designed to examine the WLB and work motivation among public servants in the Municipality of Lazi, Siquijor.

Specifically, the study would like to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the WLB of the public servants manifested in terms of the following constructs:
 - 1.1 work interference with personal life;
 - 1.2 personal life interference with work; and
 - 1.3 work personal life enhancement?
2. To what level are the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations of the public servants?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the WLB and the motivation of the public servants?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the public servants in terms of sex, civil status, number of children, and length of service, and their WLB?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

Research design. In this study, a descriptive-correlational approach was employed to delineate (a) the extent of work-life balance and (b) the extent of motivation among public servants. Additionally, it took on a correlational nature as it established relationships between the following variables: (a) the extent of work-life balance and the extent of motivation of the public servants, and (b) the profile and work-life balance of the public servants.

Research Locale

In characterizing public officials, the study took into account personnel from various national agencies, such as the PNP and the BFP, as well as permanent employees of the LGU of Lazi, across a few departments and offices.

Statistical Tools

The tools employed by the researcher to analyze the data include the following:
Weighted Mean. This was utilized to determine the extent of work-life balance and motivation among public servants.

Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. This was employed to identify the degree of relationship between (a) the extent of WLB and the motivation of public servants and (b) the profile in terms of the number of children and the extent of WLB of the public servants. This test was chosen because one of the data points was measured on an ordinal scale.

Chi-square test. This was applied to identify the relationship between the respondents' profile in terms of sex and civil status and the extent of their WLB. This test was deemed applicable since the profile variables were on a nominal scale.

Research Respondents

The study comprised 80 permanent employees from different departments, notably the department heads and assistant department heads of the Municipality of Lazi office. The survey questionnaire, which was adapted from Agha, Azmi, and Khan (2017), was also answered by employees of the National Government Agencies, such as the PNP and BFP. The Lazi Local Government Unit, comprising certain departments and national agency offices.

Research Instrument

A validated questionnaire with dependable items was used in this study to evaluate each component related to the public servants in the Municipality of Lazi. The following are the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients: 0.8 for WPLE, 0.9 for PLIW, and 0.9 for WIPL.

The following scales and descriptions were also utilized by the researcher:

For Negative Indicators

Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Work Life Balance (EoWLB)
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very Low (VL)
3.41 – 4.20	Frequent (F)	Low (L)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderately (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Rare (R)	High (H)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very High (VH)

For Positive Indicators

Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Perception (EoWLB)
4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Frequent (F)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderately (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Rare (R)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Level of Motivation (LoM)
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
2.61 – 3.40	Undecided (U)	Moderately (M)
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Data gathering procedures and analysis

The researcher followed the correct procedures for gathering data. First, an official letter of request was made, endorsed by the dean of Foundation University's graduate school, to the Lazi municipal government. After being signed and authorized, this request was given to the department heads. The researcher then gave the public servants an explanation of the questionnaire's contents, objectives, and importance. JAMOVI software was then used to process, evaluate, and interpret the data that had been gathered. In order to have a greater understanding of the perspectives of the respondents, random interviews were also performed with them. To evaluate public employees' work-life balance (WLB) and motivation, the researcher employed a weighted mean. Furthermore, the association between the number of children and WLB, as well as the degree of WLB and motivation, was investigated using the Spearman rank correlation

coefficient. One data point's ordinal character led to the selection of this test. Additionally, because the respondents' sex and marital status were on a nominal scale, the chi-square test was used to examine the association between these profile characteristics and their WLB.

RESULTS

Table 1. *Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public Servants in Terms of Work Interference with Personal Life (n=80)*

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoWLB
1. I put my personal life on hold for work	2.94	S	M
2. I miss personal activities because of work	2.90	S	M
3. My personal life suffers because of work	2.69	S	M
4. My job affects my mental and physical health	2.65	S	M
5. I struggle to juggle work and non-work	2.60	R	H
6. I neglect personal needs because of work	2.59	R	H
7. I am unhappy with the amount of time for non-work activities.	2.38	R	H
Composite	2.68	S	M

Table 1 shows the extent of the public servants' WLB in terms of work interference with their personal lives, which includes putting personal lives on hold, missing personal activities because of work, suffering in personal life because of work, and job impacts on mental and physical health.

Table 2. *Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public Servants in Terms of Personal Life Interference with Work (n = 80)*

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoWLB
1. My personal life drains me of energy for work	2.44	R	H
2. I am too tired to be effective at work	2.19	R	H
3. It is hard to work because of personal matters.	2.01	R	H
4. My work suffers because of my personal life	1.99	R	H
Composite	2.16	R	H

Table 2 displays the extent of WLB of the public servants in terms of personal life interference with work which covers feeling drained of energy for work because of personal life, being too tired to be effective at work, finding it hard to work because of personal matters, and experiencing work suffering because of personal life.

Table 3. *Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public Servants in Terms of Work Personal Life Enhancement (n = 80)*

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoWLB
1. I have a better mood because of my job.	4.11	F	H
2. My job gives me the energy to pursue personal activities	4.06	F	H
3. My personal life gives me energy for my job	4.04	F	H
4. I have a better mood at work because of my personal life	4.03	F	H
Composite	4.06	F	H

Table 3 indicates the extent to which work enhances personal life among public servants in terms of work personal life enhancement, which includes having a better mood because of the job, the job giving energy to pursue personal activities, personal life-giving energy for the job, and having a better mood at work because of personal life.

Table 4. *Level of Extrinsic Motivation of the Public Servants (n = 80)*

I am MOTIVATED to work because ...	$w\bar{x}$	VD	LoM
1. I want to make a positive impact in my field.	4.44	SA	VH
2. I want to receive positive feedback from the citizen we serve.	4.31	SA	VH
3. I want to earn a good reputation in the field of public service.	4.26	SA	VH
4. I want to be recognized for my efforts in improving our public services.	4.26	SA	VH
5. I want to secure a stable pension for my retirement.	4.21	SA	VH
6. I want to serve my community.	4.18	A	H
7. I want to be part of the solution to the challenges faced by our municipality.	4.10	A	H
8. I want to be a role model for public service in my community.	4.04	A	H
9. I want to receive commendation for my service	3.80	A	H
10. I want to contribute to the development and progress of Lazi.	3.50	A	H
Composite	4.11	A	H

Table 4 stipulates the level of extrinsic motivation among public servants in the Municipality of Lazi, Siquijor. Extrinsic motivation could come from salary, benefits, promotions, or recognition from superiors or the community.

Table 5. *Level of Intrinsic Motivation of the Public Servants (n = 80)*

I am MOTIVATED at work because...	$w\bar{x}$	VD	LoM
1. I take pride in upholding the values and principles of our local government.	4.33	SA	VH
2. I am passionate about public service and making a difference.	4.30	SA	VH
3. I find satisfaction in knowing that my work contributes to the welfare of our citizens.	4.29	SA	VH

4. I find fulfillment in serving my community.	4.26	SA	VH
5. I enjoy growing in my role as a public servant.	4.25	SA	VH
6. I am excited by the opportunity to implement innovative solutions for our community.	4.20	A	H
7. I am inspired by the resilience of our community.	4.15	A	H
8. I value the trust placed on me by the public.	4.11	A	H
9. I feel a sense of accomplishment when I see the positive impact of my work.	3.98	A	H
10. I enjoy the challenges and problem-solving aspects of my job.	3.87	A	H
Composite	4.17	A	H

Table 5 illustrates the level of intrinsic motivation among public servants. Intrinsic motivation drives come from within an individual, often out of interest or enjoyment.

Table 6 Relationship between the Work-Life Balance and the Extrinsic Motivation of Public Servants (n=80)

Variables	Coefficients	SE	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	2.757	0.332	8.314	0.000
WIPL	-0.055	0.121	-0.460	0.647
PLIW	0.034	0.118	0.287	0.775
WPLE	0.355	0.068	5.217	0.000

R = 0.5147

R² = 0.2649

adjusted R² = 0.2359

F-ratio = 9.129

p-value = 0.000 (**significant**)

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 6 presents a perception of the relationship between the WLB and the extrinsic motivation of the public servants, which is measured in terms of WIPL, PLIW, and WPLE.

Table 7. Relationship between the Work-Life Balance and the Intrinsic Motivation of Public Servants (n=80)

Variables	Coefficients	SE	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	3.080	0.344	8.959	0.000
WIPL	-0.058	0.125	-0.467	0.642
PLIW	0.047	0.122	0.385	0.701
WPLE	0.283	0.071	4.013	0.000

R = 0.4188
 R² = 0.1753
 Adjusted R = 0.1428
 F-ratio = 5.388
 p-value = 0.002 (**significant**)

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 7 offers a thorough analysis of the relationship between WLB and intrinsic motivation.

Table 8. Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of WIPL of the Public Servants (n = 80)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	2.192	0.178	12.327	0.000
Sex	0.084	0.159	0.526	0.601
Civil Status	0.092	0.189	0.487	0.628
No. of Children	0.052	0.064	0.818	0.416
Length of Service	0.024	0.010	2.411	0.018

R = 0.3668
 R² = 0.1345
 Adjusted R = 0.0884
 F-ratio = 2.915
 p-value = 0.027 (**significant**)

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 8 disclose the relationship between the profile and the work-life balance of the public servants in terms of WIPL.

Table 9. Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of PLIW of the Public Servants (n = 80)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	1.696	0.185	9.173	0.000
Sex	0.108	0.165	0.654	0.515
Civil Status	0.128	0.196	0.654	0.515
No. of Children	0.027	0.066	0.399	0.691
Length of Service	0.022	0.010	2.166	0.054

R = 0.3303
 R² = 0.1091
 Adjusted R = 0.0616
 F-ratio = 2.295
 p-value = 0.067 (**not significant**)

Level of significance = 0.05

The information shown in Table 9 clarifies the connection between the profile and the WLB of the public servants in terms of PLIW.

Table 10. Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of WPLE of the Public Servants (n = 80)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	3.937	0.186	21.177	0.000
Sex	-0.059	0.166	-0.353	0.725
Civil Status	-0.013	0.197	-0.068	0.946
No. of Children	-0.030	0.067	-0.446	0.657
Length of Service	0.016	0.010	1.545	0.127

R = 0.1779
 R² = 0.0316
 Adjusted R = 0.0200
 F-ratio = 0.613
 p-value = 0.655 (**not significant**)

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 10 stipulates the relationship between the profile and the WLB of the public servants in terms of WPLE.

DISCUSSION

Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public Servants in Terms of Work Interference with Personal Life

The benefit of work interference with personal life is professional growth. This is supported by Smith (2021) who asserted that those professionals who put more time into work-related activities beyond their regular work hours can see significant professional growth such as attending a seminar or workshop and the like.

As revealed, the extent of work-life balance is “Moderate to High” as made evident by the values of the weighted mean ranging from 2.38 to 2.94. The (VD) is “Sometimes” and the EoWLB is “Moderate”. This finding suggests that public servants sometimes experience work-related concerns over their personal life concerns and work interference with their personal is professional growth. This is supported by Smith (2021), professionals who voluntarily devote more time to work-related activities outside of regular working hours can see significant professional growth such as attending workshops or working on skill-building projects.

Extent of Work-Life Balance of Public Servants in Terms of Personal Life Interference with Work

The data reflect that the extent of WLB got a high rating ($w\bar{x}=2.44$) in terms of feeling drained of energy for work because of personal life. This signifies that public servants are able to effectively manage their personal lives and work commitments.

This result affirmed the statement of Makhmut (2020) who defined that WLB encompasses leisure, family, religion, and job. Personal and work life must be equally balanced to prevent an employee from possible burnout. Aside from that, work-life balance occurs when a lack of conflict between work and family occurs (Au et. al.,2020; Weale et. al., 2020).

Extent of Work-Life Balance of the Public Servants in Terms of Work Personal Life Enhancement

As revealed in the table, the public servants find that their work enhances their personal lives with a weighted mean ranging from 4.03 to 4.11. This is a positive finding, indicating that public servants are able to effectively manage their work and personal lives in a way that mutually benefits each other. As theorized by Johnson and Smith (2021), enhancing work-life integration provides several advantages. Their study found that employees who have the freedom to handle personal matters during work hours, such as attending doctor’s appointments or taking care of family obligations, are said to have the feeling of being more integrated with work and personal lives. Because of this, the employee can attend and complete personal duties without taking a lot of time off or leaving work.

Level of Extrinsic Motivation of the Public Servants

As reflected in the table, the public servants “Strongly Agree” that public servants are highly motivated by these extrinsic factors with a weighted mean of 4.44, which ranks number 1 among the other indicators. Public servants are driven by the desire to serve their community, contribute to their field, and receive recognition for their efforts. This high level of extrinsic motivation can lead to increased job satisfaction and performance among

public servants. The results only suggest that public servants are highly motivated by these extrinsic factors with a composite weighted mean of 4.11. This is corroborated by Asaari, MHAH, et. al., (2019) who posited that reward and motivation have a strong relationship in the attainment of the goals of an organization.

Given the high level of extrinsic motivation among public servants in Lazi, it is important to continue recognizing and rewarding their efforts. Additionally, providing opportunities for professional development and career advancement can further enhance their motivation and job satisfaction.

Level of Intrinsic Motivation of the Public Servants

The data suggest that public servants possess very high extent of motivation due to various factors. Meanwhile, the other half of the indicators, from numbers six to 10, got a weighted mean ranging from 3.87 to 4.20, described as “high.”. The results affirm the statements of Ryan and Deci (2000) that when an individual is motivated by their own intrinsic interests and enjoyment of the activities rather than by outside rewards or outcomes, they are said to be motivated intrinsically. In other words, the public servants are driven by the desire to serve their community, contribute to their field, and receive recognition for their efforts. This high level of intrinsic motivation can lead to increased job satisfaction and performance among public servants.

Summing up, the results indicate that the public servants in Lazi are highly motivated by external factors such as recognition and feedback, but also have a strong intrinsic motivation driven by personal values and a sense of purpose. This means that a combination of external recognition and internal satisfaction plays a crucial role in motivating public servants in Lazi. This result is likewise evident in the study of Mahmoud et al. (2020) wherein both personal and professional motivations are positively impacted by WLB in an indirect way. WLB is important for the company or agencies since it impacts employees' motivation and capacity to stay committed to their work. As emphasized by Shafee et al. (2020), WLB and work motivation must also be balanced.

Relationship between the Work-Life Balance and the Extrinsic Motivation of Public Servants

Using Multiple Linear Regression Analysis, the researcher found that the F-test significance or overall p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that the sample data provide enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis for the entire population. This signifies that the public servants in terms of WPLE perceive their work as enhancing their personal life and that they are more likely to be extrinsically motivated. This could be because a positive WLB can lead to increased job satisfaction, which in turn can enhance extrinsic motivation. Similarly, Lumunon et al. (2019) postulated that having a healthy WLB means that a person can balance their personal

and professional obligations. Achieving and maintaining a balance between personal and professional lives become increasingly important (Juliarti & Anindita, 2022).

The data further reveal that both WIPL and PLIW components of WLB do not significantly relate to the extent of extrinsic motivation of the public servants (all p-values $> \alpha = 0.05$). This means that the WPLE is likely more significant than WIPL, and PLIW directly relates to the positive aspects of WLB. Public servants who feel that their work enhances their personal life, such as by providing a sense of fulfillment or opportunities for personal growth, are more likely to be motivated extrinsically. On the other hand, the lack of significance for WIPL and PLIW suggests that while work and personal life interactions exist, they may not strongly influence extrinsic motivation among public servants in Lazi.

Relationship between the Work-Life Balance and the Intrinsic Motivation of Public Servants

This means that some of the explanatory or independent variables are significant predictors of the public servants' intrinsic motivation. Assessing the regression output, the researcher found that the extent of the public servants' work-personal life enhancement (WPLE) ($p = 0.000$) is the only predictor of their intrinsic motivation. This suggests that some of the explanatory or independent variables are significant predictors of the public servants' intrinsic motivation.

According to Ryan and Deci (2000), when an individual is motivated by their own intrinsic interests and enjoyment of the activities rather than by outside rewards or outcomes, they are said to be motivated intrinsically. In the context of public servants in the municipality of Lazi, intrinsic motivation could be driven by a desire to serve the community, uphold public values, and make a positive impact on society.

However, WPLE is likely more significant than WIPL and PLIW in influencing intrinsic motivation because it directly relates to the positive aspects of WLB. Public servants who feel that their work enhances their personal life, such as by providing a sense of fulfillment or opportunities for personal growth, are more likely to be intrinsically motivated. In contrast, the lack of significance for WIPL and PLIW suggests that while work and personal life interactions exist, they may not strongly influence intrinsic motivation among public servants in Lazi.

Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of WIPL

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Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of PLIW

It is identified that the F-test significance or overall p-value (0.067) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This means that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This further connotes that the profile variables cannot be considered as significant predictors of the public servants' WLB in terms of PLIW. Perrigino et al. (2018) argued that the study of WLB remains snowed under by a lack of conceptual clarity.

Lastly, the results indicate that there is no significant relationship between the profile variables (sex, civil status, number of children, and length of service) and work-life balance (PLIW). The coefficients for all variables, including length of service, are not statistically significant, indicating that these variables do not have a significant impact on personal life interference with work among public servants in Lazi. This suggests that factors other than those measured in this study may influence the level of personal life interference with work. Therefore, the length of service alone may not be a reliable predictor of personal life interference with work among public servants in the Municipality of Lazi.

Relationship between the Profile and Work-Life Balance in Terms of WPLE

It is shown that the F-test significance or overall p-value (0.655) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This means that the data are not sufficient to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, the profile variables cannot be considered significant determinants of the public servants' WLB in terms of WPLE.

The findings suggest that demographic and employment factors such as sex, civil status, number of children, and length of service do not have a significant impact on how work interferes with personal life enhancement (WPLE) among public servants in Lazi. This also implies that regardless of these factors, public servants in the municipality tend to perceive their personal lives as not significantly enhanced by their work. Factors such

as gender, marital status, family size, and length of service do not seem to play a major role in shaping this aspect of WLB for these employees.

The study by Le et al. (2020) focused more on striking a balance between paid employment and personal and family obligations to achieve a holistic sense of well-being, including family happiness, psychological health, and general life satisfaction. Bhumika (2020) also stated that balancing work and personal duties are undoubtedly one of today's most urgent concerns on a global scale.

The results signify that the profile variables (sex, civil status, number of children, and length of service) do not have a significant impact on work interference with personal life (WPLE) among public servants in the Municipality of Lazi. Specifically, none of the coefficients for these variables are statistically significant, suggesting that factors other than those considered in this study may influence the level of work interference with personal life. Additionally, the sample size of 80 respondents may not have been large enough to detect significant relationships between these profile variables and WLB in terms of WPLE.

Conclusions

This study reveals important insights about WLB and motivation among public servants in the Municipality of Lazi. Those who are holding managerial positions in the LGU unavoidably have to prioritize first their work responsibilities over personal life concerns, occasionally. This is because these public servants took an oath to deliver effective and efficient basic services to the public. The extrinsic and intrinsic motivation of the public servants is high in terms of work enhancement and personal life. This confirms the concept of competence underscored by the Self-determination Theory. The enhancement imparted in the workplace contributes to the personal life of public servants. The study highlights that enhancing WLB significantly predicts motivation. Specifically, longer-serving public servants face distinct challenges related to work interference with personal life. This is because, through the years, tenured employees can adjust and come up with ways to juggle work responsibilities without compromising the quality of personal life. These findings emphasize the need to prioritize WLB initiatives to boost motivation and job satisfaction among public servants. Tailoring interventions based on profile variables, especially considering the length of service, can further address specific needs in Lazi.

Recommendations

Adopting targeted work-life balance (WLB) programs—such as flexible scheduling and stress reduction initiatives—that address areas of moderate job interference with personal life is advised in order to improve the well-being and performance of public officials in Lazi, Siquijor. A pleasant work atmosphere can be created by honoring and recognizing employee accomplishments through service awards and recognition

programs. Specific WLB difficulties can be addressed by customizing treatments based on length of service, such as mentoring programs for those with longer service. It is essential to regularly evaluate WLB and motivation, in addition to cultivating an environment in the workplace that appreciates WLB. It is also advised to carry out more research and submit findings for program implementation to regional and federal government offices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher carefully assessed all requisite ethical considerations throughout the study's duration. Coding of the respondents and ensuring the confidentiality of their responses were also duly accounted for. Moreover, the respondents were courteously invited to partake in the study, and their consent to utilize their responses was obtained.

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REFERENCES

- Agha, K., Azmi, F. T. & Khan, S. A. (2017). Work-Life Balance: Scale Development and Validation. In: Heras, M. L., Chinchilla, N. & Grau, M. (eds). *The Work-Family Balance in Light of Globalization and Technology* (pp. 109-130). Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK
- Asaari, MHAH, Desa, N.M., Subramaniam L. (2019). Influence of Salary, Promotion, and Recognition toward Work Motivation among Government Trade Agency Employees. *International Journal of Business and Management*; Vol. 14, No. 4; 2019 ISSN 1833-3850 E-ISSN 1833-8119 Published by Canadian Center of Science and Education.
- Bhumika (2020), "*Challenges for work-life balance during COVID-19 induced nationwide lockdown: exploring gender difference in emotional exhaustion in the Indian setting*", *Gender in Management*, Vol. 35 Nos 7/8, pp. 705-718, doi: 10.1108/GM-06-2020-0163.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). *The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior*. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Au, W.C., Ayudhya, U.C.N., Tan, Y.S. and Ahmed, P.K. (2020), "*The work-life experiences of an invisible workforce*", *Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion: An International Journal*, Vol. 39 No. 5, pp. 567-583, doi: 10.1108/EDI-02-2019-0059.
- Hite, L. M., & McDonald, K. S. (2020). Careers after COVID-19: Challenges and changes. *Human Resource Development International*, 23(4), 427-437.
- Johnson, S. M., & Smith, J. D. (2021). "The impact of work-life integration on employee productivity." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 106(3), 365-378.
- Juliarti, N. P. T., & Anindita, R. (2022). *Peran Kepemimpinan Karismatik dan Work-Life Balance Terhadap Komitmen Organisasional Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan pada Industri Broadcasting*. JENIUS (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia), 5(2), 298. <https://doi.org/10.32493/JJSDM.v5i2.16509>
- Larastrini, P. M., & Adnyani, I. G. A. D. (2019). *Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Lingkungan Kerja Dan Work-Life Balance Terhadap Loyalitas Karyawan* (Doctoral dissertation, Udayana University)
- Le, H., Newman, A., Menzies, J., Zheng, C. and Fermelis, J. (2020), "*Work-life balance in Asia: a systematic review*", *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 30 No. 4, pp. 1053-4822, doi: 10.1016/j.hrmr.2020.100766.
- Lumunon, R.R., Sendow, G.M., & Uhing, Y. (2019). The Effect of Work Life Balance, Occupational Health and Workload on Employee Job Satisfaction at PT. Tirta Investama (Danone) AQUA Airmadidi. *Journal of Economics, Management, Business, And Administration (EMBA)*, 7(4), 4671–4680.
- Makhmut, K. D. I. (2020). Pengaruh Beban Kerja dan Konflik Peran terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Kantor Pelayan Pajak Pratama Jember dengan Work Life Balance sebagai Variabel Intervening. Skripsi. Universitas Jember. Diakses dari <https://repository.unej.ac.id/handle/123456789/101384>.

- Mahmoud, A. B., Fuxman, L., Mohr, I., Reisel, W. D., & Grigoriou, N. (2020). "We aren't your reincarnation!" workplace motivation across X, Y and Z generations. *International Journal of Manpower*.
- Olugu, M. U., Audu, A. T., Akubo, P. E., and Akintola, S. K. (2018). *Influence of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards on organizational performance in Nigeria*. *Int. J. Adv. Res. Sci. Eng.* 7, 26–39. Available at: <https://doc.presentica.com/12029496/5ec2160b32996.pdf>.
- Perrigino, M.B., Dunford, B.B. and Wilson, K.S. (2018), "Work-family backlash: the 'dark side' of work-life balance (WLB) policies", *Academy of Management Annals*, Vol. 12 No. 2, pp. 600-630, doi: 10.5465/annals.2016.0077.
- Weale, V., Oakman, J. and Wells, Y. (2020), "*Can organizational work–life policies improve work–life interaction? A scoping review*", *Australian Psychologist*, Vol. 55 No. 5, pp. 425-439, doi: 10.1111/ ap.12469.